

FERRAMENTA PARA CRIAÇÃO DE RESUMOS

ABSTRACT MAKER TOOL (A. M. T.)

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There are different ways that the authors can present the abstract of a manuscript. However, with the evolution of the journal and the passing of time, the Periódico Tchê Química adopted the structured format of the abstract.

The structured abstract is intended to be comprehensive, providing a logical order for the presentation of scientific communication. It also provides the readers with a summary of the research background, objectives, methods, results, and conclusions. It is not complicated to do, but frequently the authors may forget to include parts of its content; therefore, this tool was developed, so the authors can enjoy the writing of the abstract in a very straightforward way.

To access the AMT environment at tchequimica.com, please click on the highlighted icon from figure 1, or type the link < https://www.tchequimica.com/en/abstract_maker.php >.

Figure 1. Locating the AMT icon at the website.

When exploring the environment of the A. M. T. (script version 1.3), the authors will initially find a collection of text boxes to include the proper text (background, aims...), as in Figure 2.

Abstract maker tool

Script version 1.2

Please fill in the boxes below to prepare an abstract. It is easy as 1, 2, and 3!

(Step 1). Please, type the sections of the abstract in the boxes below.

Background:

Describe the Background/Introduction here. Sample text: "Energy production is a world-class problem. Renewable fuels can contribute to increasing the amount of available energy..."

450 characters remaining in your input limit.

Aims:

Describe the Aims of the research here. Sample text: "The aim of this project was to increase the production of renewable fuels with the reduction of the input of energy..."

200 characters remaining in your input limit.

Figure 2. Textfield introduction areas for the abstract maker tool.

If the authors have a browser with a dictionary or spellchecker installed, recommendations for text corrections will be made available instantaneously.

After completing the text boxes, the authors will locate a submission button, as in Figure 3. It is expected that the authors press the submit button.

that increase the production yield, the the increase of the temperature had 10% more production than the increase in the agitation speed...". Sample text (for REVIEW PAPER): "Around 70% of the authors claim that the increase of the temperature in the production of biodiesel has a positive effect... while 6% say it has

400 characters remaining in your input limit.

Conclusions:

Describe the Conclusions here. Sample text: "it was concluded that the transesterification reaction can produce biodiesel and increase the global energy supply..."

250 characters remaining in your input limit.

SUBMIT

Figure 3. Submit button to generate the text paragraph.

After pressing the submit button, the authors should go to step 2. In step 2, it is possible to see the abstract generated with the previously informed text, according to Figure 4.

(Step 2). Now, how about you just copy and paste your newly generated abstract in the word counter box? By doing so you can check if your abstract is not too big or too short.

Background: Sample text, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean facilisis, metus quis tincidunt fermentum, sem massa condimentum massa, dapibus gravida neque justo fringilla justo. Nulla facilisi. Maecenas posuere ipsum sed metus lacinia, vitae dictum dolor cursus. Sed eget justo ac nisl consectetur tristique ut sed ex. Mauris diam ipsum, convallis id euismod eu, tempus sit amet urna. Morbi tellus elit, mollis sed dolor nec, mattis f **Aims:** Sample text, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean facilisis, metus quis tincidunt fermentum, sem massa condimentum massa, dapibus gravida neque justo fringilla justo. Nulla **Methods:** Sample text, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean facilisis, metus quis tincidunt fermentum, sem massa condimentum massa, dapibus gravida neque justo fringilla justo. Nulla facilisi. Maecenas posuere ipsum sed metus lacinia, vitae dictum dolor cursus. Sed eget justo ac nisl consectetur tristique ut sed ex. Mauris diam ipsum, convallis id euismod eu, tempus sit amet urna. Morbi tellus elit, mollis sed dolor nec, mattis f **Results:** Sample text, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean facilisis, metus quis tincidunt fermentum, sem massa condimentum massa, dapibus gravida neque justo fringilla justo. Nulla facilisi. Maecenas posuere ipsum sed metus lacinia, vitae dictum dolor cursus. Sed eget justo ac nisl consectetur tristique ut sed ex. Mauris diam ips. **Discussion:** Sample text, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean facilisis, metus quis tincidunt fermentum, sem massa condimentum massa, dapibus gravida neque justo fringilla justo. Nulla facilisi. Maecenas posuere ipsum sed metus lacinia, vitae dictum dolor cursus. Sed eget justo ac nisl consectetur tristique ut sed ex. Mauris diam ipsum, convallis id euismod eu, tempus sit amet urna. **Conclusions:** Sample text, Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean facilisis, metus quis tincidunt fermentum, sem massa condimentum massa, dapibus gravida neque justo fringilla justo. Nulla facilisi. Maecenas posuere ipsum sed metus lacinia

Figure 4. Paragraph preview.

As a final step, the authors can copy and paste the text into a word counter box, Figure 5. In this box, the authors can measure the abstract size if it is too extensive or too short. For example, the Southern Journal of Sciences recommends that the abstract section should have around 250 and 350 words. The word counter box also allows text edition, making the adjustments faster.

(Step 3.). Please copy and paste the text from step 2 in the textbox below to automatically count the words.

If the Word Count is among 250 and 350 congratulations, you may have done a great work.

Word Count: 313

Figure 5. Word counter box.

If the authors are satisfied with the results, they can copy and paste the abstract directly into the journal template file. Therefore, this tool assists the authors in the production of a complete, proportional, and structured abstract, making the submission and review process faster. The tool is freely available at https://www.tchequimica.com/en/abstract_maker.php.